

STATISTICAL STUDY OF POPULATION INCOMES IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: in this article, a statistical analysis of the income of the population living in the territories of the Republic of Uzbekistan and their position in the labor market is made.

Keywords: incomes of the population, labor activity, calculation of total incomes of the population, labor relations

The main goal of the economic reforms carried out in the Republic of Uzbekistan is to achieve stability and positive rates of economic development. It should be noted that all aspects of social and labor relations directly affect the lifestyle and income of the population. From a social point of view, the state conducts social policy aimed at creating conditions that ensure a decent life and free development of a person. One of the main directions of this policy is to encourage labor and entrepreneurial activity, to ensure the economic well-being of the family for every able-bodied person with their work, to create opportunities to ensure the formation of savings and their effective investment, and the standard of living and quality of the population. is to increase. Social-labor relations related to labor activity and its results have a direct impact on the formation of wages and incomes. The development of labor relations leads to the emergence of new forms of social partnership, the development of social protection, and an increase in satisfaction with work. In the stage of deepening of market relations, the standard of living of the population and the stratification of incomes become the central

problem. The direction and pace of further fundamental changes and, as a result, political stability in society will largely depend on their solution. In turn, the solution of these problems requires a clearly developed income policy. Therefore, the income policy carried out in the strata and groups of the population, It is attracting great interest in producing and non-producing structures, state (territorial) authorities, and public organizations. At the same time, economic analysis of the living standard of the population based on objective statistical data, study of monetary income and expenses of the population, level of participation of households in the economy and analysis of the classification of expenses are considered urgent issues. Necessary conditions have been created in our republic to provide social protection of 4 inhabitants, gradual increase of wages and other monetary incomes. In turn, it plays an important role in the growth of the population's monetary income, increasing its purchasing power, expanding the volume of production and ensuring stable economic development in the country. arouses great interest in state (territorial) authorities and public organizations. At the same time, economic analysis of the living standard of the population based on objective statistical data, study of monetary income and expenses of the population, level of participation of households in the economy and analysis of the classification of expenses are considered urgent issues. Necessary conditions have been created in our republic to provide social protection of 4 inhabitants, gradual increase of wages and other monetary incomes. In turn, it plays an important role in the growth of the population's monetary income, increasing its purchasing power, expanding the volume of production and ensuring stable economic development in the country. arouses great interest in state (territorial) authorities and public organizations. At the same time, economic analysis of the living standard of the population based on objective statistical data, study of monetary income and expenses of the population, level of participation of households in the economy and analysis of the classification of expenses are

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New approaches to solving problems related to the way of life of the population, labor relations in the enterprise (organization, firm, company), regulation of remuneration for labor, assessment of employee services, regulation of wages and social-labor relations in general. the use of methods of the contract predetermined the need to create a new training course for training specialists in the field of management, labor economics and sociology. The success of their practical activities is largely determined by knowledge of theoretical issues of income policy, methods and mechanisms of their formation at different levels and for different groups of the population.

The essence of income consists of a set of money payments, natural means, real estate, free services to the population in a certain period of time, which are used for consumption and savings. Monetary and in-kind incomes consist of incomes in the form of having different relative weights at different stages of the development of the country's economy. In the conditions of the market economy, a number of changes took place in the composition of the population's income:—first, the forms of income have changed, i.e. income from business activities, property, real estate, securities, foreign currency has been added to the traditional ones (salary, pension, allowance, stipend);—secondly, the quantitative and qualitative components of income have changed, features such as real owned income, accumulation and separation coefficient, income deficit, subsistence minimum, poverty level, and purchasing power of the population's monetary

income have appeared;—thirdly, new directions of income use were added: mandatory payments and contributions, expenses for the purchase of foreign currency, securities, personal property, deposits in commercial banks. At the same time, the composition of the population's income has also changed significantly. A fundamental change in ownership relations, the emergence of new forms of economic management and labor market, and investment brought about changes in the composition of the population's income.

Calculation of the total income of the population is carried out on the basis of the methodological manual developed by the State Statistics Committee based on the international statistical standards of the National Accounts System, recommendations of the International Labor Organization, and legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

According to preliminary data, as of January-September 2022, the total income of the population is 454.9 trillion. amounted to soum. In order to exclude

the influence of price factors, one of the main types of inflation indicators - the consumer price index (INI) - is used in calculating the real growth rate of the population's income. Due to changes in consumer prices, the real growth rate of the total income of the population compared to the same period last year was 110.7%.

When calculating the total income of the population, the data of the State Statistics Report, as well as the data of the economic activity of individual entrepreneurs and farmers, conducted regularly by the statistical authorities, as well as the data of the sample observation of households, in addition to the Ministry of Finance , the non-budgetary Pension Fund, the Central Bank, the People's Bank, the State Tax Committee use the aggregated information on the incomes, social payments and tax payments calculated for the population.

1- picture Total income per capita in the regions of the Republic of Uzbekistan, January-September 2022 (for nine months), thousand soums

Based on the above picture, we can say that in January-September 2022 (for nine months), the lowest indicators of total income per capita are in the Republic of Karakalpakstan (9347.8 thousand soums), Farg It was recorded in Ona (9720.7

thousand soums), Namangan (10087.7 thousand soums), Jizzakh (10575.1 thousand soums) regions.

2- picture Real growth rates of total income per capita in the Republic of Uzbekistan

As of January-September 2022 and January-September 2021, the real growth of total income per capita was 108.4%.

Figure 3. The share of territories in the income from property

In the months of January-September 2022, two-thirds of the income received from property was contributed by the city of Tashkent and amounted to 64.6%. Tashkent (7.5%) and Navoi (4.3%) regions are the regions with the next highest

share.

In short, the increase in the income of the population, the serious change in the structure of employment in economic sectors, and the expansion of the scale of informal employment are expressed. Determining the formation of these processes and determining the prospects of socio-economic development, it is possible to achieve the correct distribution of the population's income as a result of the correct organization of the distribution of local labor resources between economic sectors.

References

1. Sh.M. Mirziyoyev, we will build a free and prosperous, democratic country of Uzbekistan together. T. Uzbekistan 2016, pp. 15-16
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Employment, T. 1998
3. FN Achilov Prospective directions of ensuring employment of the population and raising the standard of living of the population "Oriental Art and Culture" Scientific-Methodical Journal - (1) IV/2019
4. www.stat.uz

